
JWTForge: A JWT Vending Service for Testing, Fuzzing, and Security Research of OAuth2/OIDC Implementations

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1 Abstract

JSON Web Token (JWT) implementations of OAuth2 and OpenID Connect (OIDC) are a frequent source of authentication vulnerabilities, yet systematic testing remains constrained by the absence of automated, programmable token generation infrastructure. This paper presents JWTForge, an open-source HTTP service generating cryptographically signed JWT tokens with configurable claim structures, header parameters, and adversarial payloads, deployable on Cloudflare Workers. JWTForge provides three testing modes: compliant mode produces realistic OIDC tokens via Faker; fuzz mode injects Big List of Naughty Strings and boundary values into claims and headers; malicious mode substitutes domain-specific injection payloads including SQL injection, XSS, path traversal, command injection, LDAP, NoSQL, XXE, and algorithm confusion variants into token claims and headers. The service supports three token generation approaches: JSON payload, OAuth2 client credentials, and token exchange with claim transformation. Additional capabilities include token introspection, OIDC discovery and JWKS endpoints, and automated RSA/Elliptic Curve key rotation. By addressing token generation rather than manipulation, JWTForge enables construction of reproducible token corpora for integration testing, robustness evaluation, and vulnerability research. Evaluation demonstrates practical utility in systematically testing JWT implementations against vulnerabilities including algorithm confusion attacks, claim injection vulnerabilities, and authorization flaws aligned with OWASP Top 10. Performance benchmarks demonstrate JWTForge can handle sustained high-throughput with low latency on a moderate hardware, making it suitable for CI/CD integration, testing automation, and fuzzing campaigns at production scale.

2 Keywords

JWT, OAuth2, OIDC, security testing, fuzzing, token generation, token exchange, token introspection, authentication, penetration testing, algorithm confusion, injection attacks, BLNS, Cloudflare Workers

3 Introduction

Modern web applications rely extensively on OAuth2 [1] and OpenID Connect [2] for authentication and authorization. These protocols use JSON Web Tokens (JWT) [3] to

convey cryptographically signed claims between identity providers and resource servers. Access control vulnerabilities represent a critical security concern: according to the OWASP Top 10 for 2025 [4], broken access control is ranked as the number one security risk, with 100% of tested applications found to have some form of access control vulnerability. A significant class of these vulnerabilities involves manipulation of JWT tokens — attackers replay or tamper with JWT access control tokens, manipulate metadata, or exploit missing authorization checks to elevate privileges or perform unauthorized operations.

Despite the ubiquity of JWT-based authentication, the security properties of JWT implementations vary substantially. RFC 8725 [5] documents a range of implementation weaknesses — including algorithm confusion, symmetric key substitution, and missing claim validation — that have been exploited in practice across widely deployed identity systems. Common vulnerabilities include violation of the principle of least privilege, missing access controls for API operations (POST, PUT, DELETE), elevation of privilege through missing authorization checks, and exploitation of JWT invalidation mechanisms.

Systematic testing of JWT implementations is complicated by several practical constraints. Using production identity providers such as Auth0, Okta, or AWS Cognito for security testing risks exposing sensitive user data, may violate terms of service, and introduces external dependencies that undermine test reproducibility. Manually constructing JWT tokens for edge-case testing is labor-intensive and prone to error, particularly when exploring the combinatorial space of claim types, header parameters, and encoding variations. Existing JWT-focused tools — reviewed in the Related Work section — address specific exploitation workflows but do not support automated, programmable token generation at the scale required for integration testing or fuzzing campaigns.

This paper presents JWTForge, an HTTP API service that addresses the token generation and validation phase of JWT security research. JWTForge accepts JSON-encoded claim specifications, applies configurable transformations (compliant population, fuzzing, or injection), and returns signed JWTs alongside standard OIDC infrastructure endpoints. The system supports three distinct token generation approaches: (1) direct JSON payload, (2) OAuth2 Client Credentials Grant (RFC 6749) [1], and (3) RFC 8693 token exchange [6] with optional claim transformation. The system is architected as a Cloudflare Worker [7], eliminating dedicated server management while enabling deployment within CI/CD pipelines and automated test suites. The primary contributions of this work are:

1. A modular, serverless token generation architecture supporting RSA and EC cryptography, automated key rotation, configurable claim transformation pipelines, and three distinct token generation approaches (JSON payload, OAuth2 client_credentials, RFC 8693 token exchange).
2. Three operationally distinct testing modes — compliant, fuzz, and malicious — targeting integration testing, robustness evaluation, and injection vulnerability discovery respectively.
3. A comprehensive fuzzing strategy combining BLNS patterns with domain-specific injection payloads across both JWT claims and header parameters, including algorithm confusion and KID injection vectors.
4. RFC 7662 token introspection endpoint supporting token validation, claim extraction, and expiration checking, enabling verification workflows across diverse token generation approaches.

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5. Full OIDC infrastructure support including JWKS (RFC 7517) and discovery endpoints, enabling client libraries to discover and verify JWTForge-issued tokens without manual configuration.
 6. An evaluation of JWTForge against vulnerability classes specified in RFC 8725, demonstrating its utility in identifying algorithm validation failures, claim parsing defects, injection vulnerabilities, and authorization flaws.

3.1 Workflow Scenarios

JWTForge is designed to support two primary operational workflows illustrated in **Figure 1** and **Figure 2**. As illustrated in **Figure 1**, in development environments, JWTForge integrates into continuous integration pipelines to enable automated security testing of API code changes. When a developer commits code changes to the API, the CI/CD pipeline automatically triggers a local deployment of the modified API alongside a local JWTForge instance. Postman test collections (executed via Newman or custom test runners) consume tokens generated by JWTForge and exercise the API with compliant, fuzz, and malicious test scenarios. If all security tests pass, the code is automatically promoted to beta, gamma, and production environments. Failed tests immediately notify the developer, enabling rapid iteration and regression detection before production deployment.

Figure 2 illustrates how security researchers and penetration testers can use JWTForge to systematically discover JWT vulnerabilities in target applications. The researcher configures JWTForge (locally or remotely) and designs test scenarios targeting specific vulnerability classes: algorithm confusion attacks, claim injection vulnerabilities, authorization bypass, path traversal via KID fields, and other attack vectors. JWTForge generates adversarial token payloads across all three testing modes (compliant for baseline behavior, fuzz for robustness, malicious for vulnerability discovery). Test collections execute these generated tokens against the target API, capturing response codes, error messages, latency anomalies, and other indicators of successful attacks. The researcher analyzes results to identify exploitable vulnerabilities, documents findings with reproducible test cases, and follows responsible disclosure practices to notify affected organizations.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. The Related Work section reviews existing JWT security tools. System Design and Implementation describes the architecture. Evaluation presents representative use cases and evaluation scenarios. Ethical Considerations discusses responsible use. The paper concludes with limitations and directions for future work.

4 Related Work

The JWT security tooling landscape comprises tools focused on exploitation of existing tokens, interactive token editing, and brute-force secret recovery (see Table 1). JWTForge occupies a distinct position within this ecosystem, addressing token *generation* rather than token *manipulation*.

`jwt_tool` [8] is a Python-based command-line utility for exploiting JWTs through algorithm confusion attacks (including the `alg=none` bypass), brute-force HMAC secret recovery, and claim tampering. It requires an existing JWT as input and is primarily designed for interactive exploitation workflows. Limited scripting support enables some integration into automated pipelines, but token generation from scratch is not supported.

JWT Editor [9] and **JOSEPH** [10] are Burp Suite extensions that enable interactive modification of JWT headers and payloads within intercepted HTTP traffic.

Figure 1. CI/CD pipeline integration with JWTForge. Code commits trigger automated testing using locally running JWTForge for token generation and locally running API changes for end-to-end security testing before deployment.

Figure 2. Vulnerability researcher workflow using JWTForge for systematic security testing. Researchers execute adversarial payload tests against target APIs using locally or remotely running JWTForge instances.

Both tools excel at manual penetration testing workflows but require proxy-based interception and human interaction, precluding integration into CI/CD pipelines or large-scale fuzzing campaigns.

JWT Cracker [11] focuses exclusively on brute-force recovery of HMAC-SHA256 signing secrets. It accepts a token as input and exhaustively tests candidate secrets, providing no generation or fuzzing capabilities.

Nimbus JOSE+JWT [12] and similar cryptographic libraries support programmatic JWT generation and verification but require application-level code to construct testing scenarios. They provide no built-in testing modes, fuzzing integration, or OIDC infrastructure.

JWTForge is designed to complement rather than replace these tools. A representative workflow might generate a token corpus with JWTForge and subsequently apply `jwt_tool` or JWT Editor to systematically attack individual tokens, combining generation-side automation with exploitation-side depth.

Capability	JWTForge	jwt_tool	JWT Editor	JOSEPH	JWT Cracker
Token generation	✓	×	×	×	×
Automated fuzzing	✓	Limited	×	×	×
Injection payloads	✓	×	×	×	×
Algorithm confusion	✓	✓	Partial	Partial	×
OIDC infrastructure	✓	×	×	×	×
CI/CD integration	✓	Limited	×	×	✓
Signature tampering	Partial	✓	✓	✓	×
Brute-force cracking	×	✓	×	×	✓
Serverless deployment	✓	×	×	×	×

Table 1. Comparative capabilities of JWT security tools. JWTForge occupies a distinct position within the JWT security ecosystem, addressing token *generation* rather than token *manipulation*. Checkmarks (✓) indicate full support, crosses (×) indicate no support, and “Partial” or “Limited” indicate restricted or partial functionality.

5 System Design and Implementation

JWTForge is implemented as a Cloudflare Worker in JavaScript, exposing an HTTP API for token generation and standard OIDC infrastructure endpoints. The architecture is modular, separating concerns of request parsing, claim transformation, cryptographic key management, and response formatting.

5.1 Token Generation Workflow

Token generation proceeds through five stages.

- Request Parsing:** The HTTP request body is parsed to extract JWT claims, metadata fields (`ktty`, `mode`, `response_type`, `exclude`, `header_alg`, `header_kid`), and any custom claims. Required metadata is validated; fields are categorized for downstream processing.
- OIDC Scope Processing:** When the `scope` parameter includes standard OIDC scopes (`openid`, `profile`, `email`, `address`, `phone`), JWTForge automatically populates corresponding claims using Faker.js [13]. The `openid` scope generates base claims (`sub`, `iss`, `aud`, `exp`, `iat`, `nbfi`, `jti`). The `profile` scope adds user identity claims (`name`, `given_name`, `family_name`, `picture`, `locale`, `zoneinfo`,

`birthdate`). Contact and address scopes generate structured claim objects with verification status flags. This automation eliminates manual construction of OIDC-conformant claim sets while ensuring compliance with the OIDC Core specification [2].

3. **Mode-Specific Transformations:** Based on the `mode` parameter and the caller-supplied `exclude` list, one of three transformation strategies is applied:
 - *Compliant mode* (default): Faker-generated data from Stage 2 is used without modification, producing tokens structurally conformant with RFC 7519 and OIDC Core.
 - *Fuzz mode*: One to three claims are randomly selected (excluding protected fields `iss`, `jti`, and any caller-excluded claims) and their values replaced with entries drawn uniformly at random from the BLNS corpus [14] (507 strings) augmented with additional edge cases: `null`, `undefined`, `Infinity`, `NaN`, `Number.MAX_SAFE_INTEGER`, deeply nested objects (depth ≥ 5), large arrays (≥ 100 elements), and numeric boundary values.
 - *Malicious mode*: One to three claims are selected and replaced with domain-specific injection payloads drawn from ten categories: SQL injection, cross-site scripting (XSS), path traversal, OS command injection, LDAP injection, NoSQL injection, XML external entity (XXE), server-side template injection (SSTI), HTTP header injection, and buffer overflow patterns.
4. **Header Processing:** When `header_alg` or `header_kid` are present alongside fuzz or malicious modes, additional transformations are applied to the JWT header:
 - *Fuzz mode for alg*: Generates algorithm confusion variants including `none`, `None`, `NONE`, `nOnE`, `HS256`, `HS384`, `HS512` (symmetric key confusion), `RS384`, `RS512`, `ES384`, `ES512`, `PS256`, empty string, and BLNS-derived patterns.
 - *Malicious mode for alg*: Alternates between `none` and injection payloads.
 - *Fuzz/malicious mode for kid*: Injects BLNS patterns, SQL injection, XSS, path traversal, and null-byte sequences.
5. **Signing and Response:** Modified claims are assembled with the JWT header. The private key is retrieved from the storage backend (Section 3.2). The JWT is signed using the Web Crypto API [15]. The response includes the signed token, token type, and expiration timestamp. For hybrid flows (`response_type=id_token token`), both access and ID tokens are generated independently.

The complete token generation workflow is illustrated in Figure 3.

5.2 Cryptographic Key Management

JWTForge supports RSA (RS256) and Elliptic Curve (ES256) key types [16], selected per request via the `key` parameter. Key lifecycle management varies by deployment context.

In production deployments on Cloudflare Workers, keys are stored in Workers KV [17] or optionally in Durable Objects [18]. Keys rotate automatically every 24 hours, with a 6-hour grace period during which superseded keys remain valid in the JWKS endpoint, accommodating eventual consistency propagation across the Cloudflare network. Multiple active keys are simultaneously published to JWKS, allowing clients

Figure 3. JWTForge token generation workflow. Three distinct token generation approaches (JSON payload, OAuth2 client credentials, RFC 8693 token exchange) converge to a common signing workflow. Solid arrows indicate primary flow; dashed arrows indicate conditional paths.

to verify tokens signed by either the current or immediately preceding key. 202
Deterministic key generation via seeded pseudorandom number generators supports 203
reproducible test scenarios. 204

In local development environments (via `wrangler dev`), keys are held in memory and 205
regenerated on each server restart, providing a stateless development experience without 206
persistent storage dependencies. 207

The storage abstraction layer (`storage.js`) presents a uniform interface regardless of 208
backend, allowing deployment context to be changed without modifying token 209
generation logic. Workers KV [17] is the default backend, available at no cost on the 210
Cloudflare free tier; Durable Objects [18] provide strongly consistent transactional 211
storage for deployments with stricter consistency requirements. 212

5.3 Token Generation Approaches 213

JWTForge supports three operationally distinct approaches to token generation, 214
enabling diverse testing workflows: 215

1. **Direct JSON Payload:** Clients submit token claims as a JSON object in the 216
request body. This approach provides maximum flexibility for claim specification 217
and is suitable for unit testing, integration testing, and adversarial payload 218
injection scenarios. Custom claims, OIDC scopes, and transformation modes are 219
all supported. 220
2. **OAuth2 Client Credentials Grant (RFC 6749):** Clients authenticate using 221
HTTP Basic authentication 222
(`Authorization: Basic base64(client_id:client_secret)`) and request tokens via 223
form-encoded parameters, specifying `grant_type=client_credentials` and optional 224
`scope` and `sub` parameters. This approach enables testing of OAuth2-compliant 225
token endpoints and role-based authorization flows without requiring explicit 226
claim specification, as base claims are auto-generated. This testing mode is 227
particularly valuable for validating client credential flows and client authentication 228
mechanisms. 229
3. **Token Exchange (RFC 8693):** Clients submit a subject token (JWT, ID token, 230
or access token) along with desired token type transformations and optional claim 231
modifications (`add_claims` and `remove_claims` parameters). This approach enables 232
testing of token exchange scenarios, delegation flows, and claim transformation 233
logic without requiring access to the original token issuer. The introspection 234
endpoint can validate the exchanged tokens, providing a complete token exchange 235
workflow. 236

5.4 Token Introspection 237

JWTForge implements RFC 7662 token introspection [19], providing token validation 238
and claim inspection across all token generation approaches. The introspection endpoint 239
(`POST /introspect`) accepts a token and optional token type hint, validates the token 240
signature using available public keys, checks expiration and not-before times, and 241
returns a JSON response containing the token's validity status (`active: true/false`) 242
and all token claims. Introspection supports Basic authentication using the same client 243
credentials format as the OAuth2 `client_credentials` grant. This endpoint enables 244
verification workflows where tokens generated by any approach can be validated and 245
inspected without requiring the original issuer's verification endpoint. The complete 246
token introspection flow is illustrated in Figure 4. 247

Figure 4. JWTForge token validation workflow. The introspection endpoint validates tokens by verifying signatures using JWKS-published keys, checking expiration times, and returning active status and claims.

5.5 OIDC Infrastructure Endpoints

JWKS Endpoint (`/.well-known/jwks.json`): Returns a JSON Web Key Set [20] containing all currently active public keys. Each entry includes key type (`kt`), algorithm (`alg`), intended use (`use: sig`), key identifier (`kid`), and algorithm-appropriate key material (`n, e` for RSA; `x, y` for EC). Clients use this endpoint for automated public key discovery. The JWKS endpoint includes keys in both grace periods and active rotation states to accommodate eventual consistency in distributed deployments.

OIDC Discovery Endpoint (`/.well-known/openid-configuration`): Returns an OpenID Connect Provider Metadata document [21] specifying the issuer URL, token endpoint, introspection endpoint, JWKS URI, supported response types (`token, id_token, id_token token`), subject types, supported ID token signing algorithms (`RS256, ES256`), and supported token endpoint authentication methods (`none, http_basic`). Standard OIDC client libraries can configure themselves automatically against a deployed JWTForge instance without manual endpoint specification.

5.6 Deployment

JWTForge is distributed as an open-source repository deployable to Cloudflare Workers via the Wrangler CLI or through an automated deployment workflow. Local development requires Node.js 18 or later. The service is also available as a hosted instance at <https://jwtforge.dev> with interactive OpenAPI documentation at the root URL, as shown in Figure 5.

5.7 API Documentation

JWTForge provides interactive API documentation through Swagger UI, accessible at the service root URL. The Swagger interface includes example token templates for representative testing scenarios and enables token generation and testing directly from the browser without command-line tooling.

A complete example demonstrating JWTForge usage for testing OAuth2-protected APIs is available at <https://github.com/axioms-io/axioms-fastapi/tree/main/example>, showing integration of JWTForge-generated tokens in an automated testing pipeline for OAuth2 resource servers.

5.8 Performance Characteristics

JWTForge is architected for high-throughput token generation. Local performance testing on Mac M2 Pro 16 GB demonstrates sustained throughput of 586 requests/second with 12ms average response time and zero error rate across 74,315 requests (see Figure 6).

These results demonstrate that JWTForge can sustain hundreds of concurrent token generation requests with sub-20ms latency, making it suitable for integration testing, CI/CD pipelines, and moderate-scale fuzzing campaigns. The consistent performance and zero error rate indicate robust handling of sustained load without degradation or failure.

6 Evaluation

This section presents performance benchmarks and four representative scenarios demonstrating JWTForge’s utility across distinct testing objectives. Each scenario is mapped to vulnerability classes identified in RFC 8725 and the OWASP Top 10.

Figure 5. JWTForge Swagger UI. The interface provides example token templates for representative testing scenarios, enabling interactive token generation without command-line tooling.

Total requests sent ⓘ	Requests/second ⓘ	Avg. response time ⓘ	P90 ⓘ	P95 ⓘ	P99 ⓘ	Error rate ⓘ
74,315	586.01	12 ms	24 ms	31 ms	58 ms	0.00 %

Figure 6. JWTForge Performance Benchmark. Testing conducted on Mac M2 Pro 16 GB with Postman showing 586 requests/second throughput and 12ms average response time over 74,315 requests.

Note on URLs: Examples throughout this paper use <http://localhost:8787> as local authorization server. To test these, you can [clone the JWTForge repository](#) and run `npm install && npm run dev`.

6.1 Integration Testing with Compliant Tokens

Objective: Eliminate external identity provider dependencies in automated integration test suites by generating realistic, OIDC-conformant tokens locally.

- **Scenario:** A development team building a single-page application with role-based access control requires tokens representing multiple user personas — standard users, administrators, and service accounts — with realistic claim values that exercise claim parsing, scope enforcement, and role-based authorization logic.
- **Method:** Compliant mode requests with explicit scopes and role claims:

```
curl -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \  
-H "Content-Type: application/json" \  
-d '{"scope": "openid profile email", "mode": "fake", "sub": "  
test-user-1"}'  
  
curl -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \  
-H "Content-Type: application/json" \  
-d '{"scope": "openid profile email", "mode": "fake",  
"sub": "admin-user", "roles": ["admin"]}'
```

- **Outcome:** Tokens produced in this mode carry Faker-generated names, email addresses, and addresses that are structurally valid and distinct across requests, enabling test assertions on claim extraction, multi-persona authorization flows, and token expiration handling without requiring connectivity to external identity providers. Test execution is fully deterministic given the same request body, supporting reproducible CI/CD runs.

6.2 Robustness Testing via Claim and Header Fuzzing

Objective: Identify implementation defects in JWT validation logic through systematic injection of malformed and boundary-condition values.

- **Scenario:** A security team auditing a custom OAuth2 authorization server must assess robustness against malformed tokens, including those with unexpected claim types, deeply nested structures, and extreme numeric values — vulnerability classes addressed by RFC 8725 Section 3.
- **Method:** Fuzz mode is applied iteratively, with `iss` and `jti` excluded to isolate claim-level defects:

```
for i in $(seq 1 100); do  
  TOKEN=$(curl -s -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \  
    -H "Content-Type: application/json" \  
    -d '{"mode": "fuzz", "sub": "user123",  
      "exclude": ["iss", "jti"]}'} | jq -r .access_token)  
  curl -s -o /dev/null -w "%{http_code}\n" \  
    -H "Authorization: Bearer $TOKEN" \  
    https://target.example.com/protected  
done
```

- **Outcome:** Observed response patterns across the corpus reveal vulnerability classes including denial-of-service via malformed numeric claims (*Infinity*, *NaN*), type confusion errors when string-typed fields receive object or array values, unhandled null dereferences, and latency anomalies indicating expensive parsing paths. Response code distribution and error message patterns provide actionable signals for remediation without requiring source code access.

6.3 Algorithm Confusion Attack Testing

Objective: Verify that a JWT-consuming server correctly enforces algorithm validation, rejecting tokens with manipulated `alg` header fields — the primary vulnerability class documented in CVE-2015-9235 and related disclosures.

- **Method:** Three attack patterns are tested in sequence.

Algorithm none bypass:

```
curl -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \  
-H "Content-Type: application/json" \  
-d '{"sub": "user123", "header_alg": "none",  
    "exclude": ["header_alg"]}'
```

Symmetric key confusion (HS256 substitution):

```
curl -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \  
-H "Content-Type: application/json" \  
-d '{"sub": "user123", "header_alg": "HS256",  
    "exclude": ["header_alg"]}'
```

Automated algorithm variant fuzzing:

```
curl -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \  
-H "Content-Type: application/json" \  
-d '{"sub": "user123", "mode": "fuzz",  
    "header_alg": "trigger-fuzz"}'
```

The fuzz mode generates the following algorithm variants: `none`, `None`, `NONE`, `nOnE`, `HS256`, `HS384`, `HS512`, `RS384`, `RS512`, `ES384`, `ES512`, `PS256`, empty string, and BLNS-derived values.

- **Outcome:** A correctly implemented server rejects all non-configured algorithm variants, including case-insensitive forms of `none` and symmetric algorithm identifiers. Acceptance of any variant indicates a defect in the server's allowlist enforcement. This testing methodology covers the algorithm bypass class described in RFC 8725 Section 2.1 and is directly applicable to compliance verification against NIST SP 800-63B.

6.4 Injection Vulnerability Discovery via Malicious Mode

Objective: Identify injection vulnerabilities arising from unsanitized use of JWT claims in downstream operations — database queries, HTML rendering, filesystem access, or shell command construction.

- **Scenario:** A penetration tester auditing an OAuth2 resource server must determine whether token claims are treated as trusted input in security-critical operations.

- **Method:** Malicious mode targets claim fields likely to be used in downstream operations:

```
# SQL injection via email claim
curl -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \
  -H "Content-Type: application/json" \
  -d '{"mode": "malicious", "sub": "user123",
      "email": "test@example.com", "name": "Test User"}'
```

```
# KID header path traversal
curl -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \
  -H "Content-Type: application/json" \
  -d '{"mode": "malicious", "header_kid": "trigger-fuzz",
      "sub": "user123"}'
```

Malicious mode payloads for the email claim include patterns such as ' OR '1'='1, '; DROP TABLE users; --, and ' UNION SELECT NULL--. KID injection payloads include ../../../../etc/passwd, ' OR '1'='1, and null-byte-terminated path traversal sequences.

- **Outcome:** Server responses to injection-laden tokens reveal whether claims are used in raw database queries (SQL injection), HTML rendering pipelines (XSS), filesystem-based key loading (path traversal via KID), or LDAP filter construction. The injection categories correspond directly to OWASP Top 10 categories A03 (Injection) and A07 (Identification and Authentication Failures). Tokens that elicit error messages disclosing internal implementation details are separately indicative of insufficient error handling.

6.5 OAuth2 Client Credentials Testing

Objective: Validate correct implementation of OAuth2 client credentials grant flows and client authentication mechanisms.

- **Scenario:** A development team building an API server supporting OAuth2 client credentials for service-to-service authentication needs to verify correct client authentication, scope enforcement, and token issuance.
- **Method:** The client_credentials grant approach generates tokens via HTTP Basic authentication:

```
# Generate token via client_credentials grant
curl -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \
  -H "Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded" \
  -H "Authorization: Basic Y2xpZW50MTIzOmNsaWVudDEyMw==" \
  -d "grant_type=client_credentials&scope=openid%20profile"
```

```
# Validate the token using introspection
TOKEN=$(curl -s -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \
  -H "Authorization: Basic Y2xpZW50MTIzOmNsaWVudDEyMw==" \
  -d "grant_type=client_credentials" | jq -r .access_token)
```

```
curl -X POST http://localhost:8787/introspect \
  -H "Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded" \
  -H "Authorization: Basic Y2xpZW50MTIzOmNsaWVudDEyMw==" \
  -d "token=$TOKEN"
```

- **Outcome:** Correct implementation verifies that only properly authenticated clients receive tokens, that requested scopes are honored, and that the introspection endpoint correctly validates and returns claims from client_credentials-generated tokens. This testing scenario covers the client authentication class of OWASP A07.

6.6 Token Exchange and Claim Transformation

Objective: Test token exchange flows and claim transformation logic required in delegated authorization scenarios.

- **Scenario:** A security team auditing a multi-tenant API must verify correct behavior of RFC 8693 token exchange, including prevention of unauthorized claim modification and correct scope delegation.
- **Method:** The token exchange approach enables claim transformation without access to the original issuer:

```
# Generate initial JWT
INITIAL_TOKEN=$(curl -s -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \
-H "Content-Type: application/json" \
-d '{"sub": "user123", "scope": "read write"}' | jq -r .
  access_token)

# Exchange token with claim additions
EXCHANGED=$(curl -s -X POST http://localhost:8787/token \
-H "Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded" \
-d "grant_type=urn:ietf:params:oauth:grant-type:token-exchange&
  subject_token=$INITIAL_TOKEN&subject_token_type=urn:ietf:
  params:oauth:token-type:jwt&add_claims=resource:shared-
  resource" | jq -r .access_token)

# Introspect exchanged token to verify claims
curl -X POST http://localhost:8787/introspect \
-H "Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded" \
-H "Authorization: Basic Y2xpZW50MTIzOmNsaWVudDEyMw==" \
-d "token=$EXCHANGED"
```

- **Outcome:** Correct implementation preserves original claims (e.g., `sub`, `scope`), adds requested claims without replacing protected fields, and maintains proper token signatures. Introspection confirms that all expected claims are present and valid, enabling verification of delegation chains and scope restrictions across token exchange boundaries.

7 Ethical Considerations

JWTForge is a dual-use tool. The malicious mode, algorithm confusion attack generation, and KID injection capabilities are intended for security research, authorized penetration testing, and validation of defensive implementations. Their use against systems without explicit written authorization from the system owner is illegal in most jurisdictions under statutes such as the Computer Fraud and Abuse Act (CFAA) in the United States and equivalent legislation internationally.

The hosted instance at <https://jwtforge.dev> enforces rate limiting to mitigate potential misuse. Researchers using JWTForge in authorized engagements are

encouraged to document and responsibly disclose vulnerabilities discovered using the tool in accordance with established responsible disclosure frameworks such as ISO/IEC 29147 [22].

The tool is distributed under the MIT License. By publishing the implementation, the authors aim to enable defensive testing and to contribute to the broader body of knowledge on JWT implementation security, consistent with the principles of open security research.

8 Limitations and Future Work

Following are key limitations of the current implementation. None of these represent fundamental obstacles to deployment or practical utility, and many present opportunities for future enhancement to address specific operational requirements or scaling scenarios.

- **Token Verification:** JWTForge implements RFC 7662 introspection for token validation and claim extraction. While introspection provides comprehensive verification, client-side verification using the JWKS endpoint remains the responsibility of integrating applications.
- **Static Claim Generation:** Claims are fixed at generation time. Testing stateful scenarios such as incremental privilege escalation or claim evolution across token refresh cycles requires external scripting. A claims mutation API supporting field-level overrides to existing tokens would address this gap.
- **Injection Pattern Coverage:** The twenty injection categories currently implemented cover the OWASP Top 10 and common server-side injection classes, but domain-specific applications may require additional patterns. Support for user-supplied fuzzing dictionaries would enable targeted research without modifying the service.
- **Scale Constraints:** Local performance testing demonstrates sustained throughput of 586 requests/second with sub-20ms latency, suitable for integration testing and CI/CD pipelines. Cloudflare Workers impose per-request CPU time limits; at extreme generation rates (>10,000 tokens/second), these constraints may become binding. A batch generation endpoint returning multiple tokens per request would reduce per-token overhead and improve throughput for large-scale fuzzing campaigns. Distributed deployments across multiple Cloudflare edge locations would provide higher aggregate throughput for extreme-scale scenarios.
- **Storage Consistency:** The default Workers KV [17] backend is eventually consistent. The 6-hour key rotation grace period mitigates most consistency-related test failures, but deployments requiring strict consistency must use the Durable Objects [18] backend, which incurs additional cost.
- **Empirical Evaluation:** The evaluation scenarios presented above are illustrative. A systematic empirical study — applying JWTForge against a curated suite of open-source OAuth2/OIDC implementations with known CVEs — would provide stronger evidence of the tool’s effectiveness and is reserved for future work.

9 Conclusion

JWTForge addresses a gap in the JWT security testing ecosystem by providing automated, programmable token generation and validation as an HTTP API service.

Existing tools focus on the exploitation and manipulation of pre-existing tokens; JWTForge complements these by enabling construction of diverse, reproducible token corpora suited to integration testing, robustness evaluation, and injection vulnerability discovery. The three-mode architecture — compliant, fuzz, and malicious — covers distinct testing objectives within a single deployable service. Support for three distinct token generation approaches (direct JSON payload, OAuth2 client credentials, and RFC 8693 token exchange) enables comprehensive testing of OAuth2/OIDC token generation workflows. The RFC 7662 introspection endpoint provides token validation and claim inspection, completing the token lifecycle workflow. Standards-compliant OIDC infrastructure endpoints (JWKS, discovery) allow client libraries to interact with JWTForge without manual configuration. Deployment on Cloudflare Workers supports integration into CI/CD pipelines without dedicated server infrastructure. The vulnerability classes targetable by JWTForge correspond directly to those documented in RFC 8725 and the OWASP Top 10, providing a principled basis for systematic security evaluation of JWT-based authentication systems.

10 Data Availability

No primary datasets were generated or analyzed in this study. Request and response examples are documented in the project repository README and interactive API documentation.

11 Software Availability

- **Repository:** <https://github.com/abhishektiwari/jwtforge> (MIT License)
- **Hosted Service:** <https://jwtforge.dev>
- **Requirements:** Node.js 18+; Cloudflare account (free tier supported)

12 Competing Interests

No competing interests are declared.

13 Grant Information

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